

Spherical Indentation Load Relaxation in Agar Hydrogels

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Spherical indentation load relaxation in agar hydrogels is described using a combination of poroelastic and viscoelastic effects in a poroviscoelastic analysis. The effects are shown to be separable analytically and experimentally and markedly distinguish physically cross linked hydrogels from chemically cross linked hydrogels and consolidating soil foundations. The poroviscoelastic analysis is developed clearly and simply for application in experiments.

Cite as:

Cook, Robert F. (2024, August 4). Spherical Indentation Load Relaxation in Agar Hydrogels (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13210155>

1. Introduction

This brief report describes extensions to the work of [Strange et al. \(2013\)](#) that investigated load relaxation of a hydrogel during spherical indentation. Strange et al. measured time dependent load relaxation at fixed indentation strain (0.05) for three indenter radii (12.7 mm, 7.9 mm, and 3.2 mm) in water saturated 3 % (by mass) agar hydrogel. The mechanical responses were interpreted as reflecting the simultaneous actions of poroelastic effects arising from migration of water through the polymer gel network and viscoelastic effects arising from rearrangement of the network. The extensions here are both experimental and analytical. Experimentally, additional data not used in the original work are included ([Oyen, M.L, private communication 2023](#)), specifically those from an additional sphere size (4.8 mm radius) and from materials chemically altered from the base agar gel so as to impede water migration. Analytically, an empirical approximation to finite element analysis of poroelastic spherical indentation ([Hu et al. 2010](#)) is introduced and combined with a first order description of viscoelastic spherical indentation, building on the separability of these responses identified by Strange et al. The report provides strengthened support for description of time dependent deformation of physically cross linked hydrogels by a combination of poroelastic and viscoelastic mechanisms ([Galli et al. 2011](#); [Strange et al. 2013](#)).

The report is divided into a further two major sections. Section 2 provides a summary of the expressions used here to describe poro- and visco-elastic spherical indentation. Connections to analyses leading to these expressions are made by references to other works. Section 3 demonstrates application of the expressions to experimental observations of load relaxation in agar hydrogels. Connections to related experiments are made by references to other works.

2. Analysis

2.1 Elastic Deformation

Analysis begins with the equilibrium relationship between the normal load P and contact radius a for a sphere of radius R on the surface of an isotropic linear elastic material. This is the Hertzian relationship and is conventionally written as ([Johnson, 1985](#))

$$P = \frac{4E^*a^3}{3R}, \quad (1)$$

where E^* is the “indentation” or “reduced” modulus. For a rigid indenter, E^* devolves to the plane strain modulus of the material

$$E^* = \frac{E}{(1 - \nu^2)}, \quad (2)$$

where E and ν are the Young’s (plane stress) modulus and Poisson’s ratio of the material, respectively. The relationship between Young’s modulus and shear modulus G of the material is

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}. \quad (3)$$

Combining Eqs. (1)–(3) thus gives

$$P = \frac{8Ga^3}{3(1 - \nu)R}. \quad (4)$$

The stress and strain fields in an indented material are inhomogeneous. However, a convenient measure of indentation deformation is the “characteristic indentation strain” ε defined as $\varepsilon = 0.2a/R$. Hence Eq. (4) can be expressed as

$$P = \frac{8G}{3(1 - \nu)} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{0.2} \right)^3 R^2, \quad (5)$$

which separates material parameters from experimental parameters. The experimental utility of Eq. (5) is enhanced by recognizing that the contact and sphere radii are related by the experimentally controllable contact depth h through $a^2 = Rh$, such that an imposed indentation strain is given by $\varepsilon = 0.2(h/R)^{1/2}$ (there is a typographical error in Strange et al. 2013).

Nonequilibrium time dependent deformation of components is categorized between two extremes of behavior: *creep*, in which a load is imposed on the component and a dimension of the component changes with time; and *relaxation*, in which a displacement is imposed on the component and the supported load changes with time. Usually, displacement increases in creep and load decreases in relaxation. The material equivalents are increased strain on fixed stress in creep and decreased stress on fixed strain in relaxation. The experimental focus here is indentation load relaxation in which indentation depth h is maintained and decreasing indentation load $P(t)$ is monitored as a function of time t , noting that both P and h are taken as positive when directed into the material surface. The analyses used to describe load relaxation by viscoelastic and poroelastic mechanisms are now examined in turn.

2.2 Viscoelastic Deformation

A simple analytical representation of indentation load relaxation by viscoelastic processes is extension of the modulus in Eq. (5) to be a function of relaxation t time such that $G = G(t)$,

$G(t)$ is thus known as the relaxation modulus (Johnson 1985). A form that can describe many material responses is

$$G(t) = G_\infty + \Delta G_1 \exp(-t/t_1) + \Delta G_2 \exp(-t/t_2) + \dots \quad (6)$$

The ΔG_i terms characterize the amplitude of time dependent effects relative to a base value G_∞ and the t_i terms are the time constants of the relaxation modulus. The approximation used here is that there is a single $i = 1$ term notated by $\Delta G_1 = G_0 - G_\infty$, where $G_0 > G_\infty$, and $t_1 = t_V$ such that Eq. (6) becomes

$$G(t) = G_\infty + (G_0 - G_\infty) \exp(-t/t_V). \quad (7)$$

The physical meaning of the terms is noted by recognizing that for $t \gg t_V$, $G \rightarrow G_\infty$ and for $t \ll t_V$, $G \rightarrow G_0$. G_∞ is a lower bound invariant modulus that is applicable at long relaxation times when all relaxation processes have exhausted. G_∞ is thus identified with the equilibrium modulus of Eq. (5). G_0 is an upper bound modulus that is applicable at short relaxation times when relaxation processes are at their most active. G_0 is very sensitive to details of the displacement ramp prior to the relaxation process (ie for $t \leq 0$). For relaxation experiments that can be approximated by imposition of a step displacement G_0 is an inferred initial modulus. Incorporation of G_0 or G_∞ into Eq. (5) results in upper and lower bound loads during indentation relaxation of P_0 and P_∞ , respectively, and the load relaxation is described by

$$P(t) = P_\infty + (P_0 - P_\infty) \exp(-t/t_V). \quad (8)$$

2.3 Poroelastic Deformation

Aspects of poroelastic mechanics are first summarized here to provide background and context for the following indentation load relaxation description. Detailed analyses can be found elsewhere (Detournay and Cheng 1993; Wang 2000; Howell et al. 2009).

The local elastic strain energy density \mathcal{U}_E (energy/volume) in a porous linear elastic solid containing a compressible fluid is given by

$$\mathcal{U}_E = G \left[\varepsilon_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} + \frac{\nu}{1 - 2\nu} (\varepsilon_k k)^2 \right] + \frac{K_f \zeta^2}{2}. \quad (9)$$

The first term represents the strain energy in the solid, here taken to be the polymer chain hydrogel skeleton, and the second term represents the strain energy in the fluid, here taken to be the interstitial water. G and ν are the shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of the drained solid and K_f is the bulk modulus of the fluid. ε_{ij} is the strain in the solid and the Einstein repeated index summation convention is used. ζ is the variation in fluid volume relative to that of a hydrogel material element, and can be interpreted similarly to a dilatational strain. Local stress σ_{ij} is given

by partial differentiation of the local energy density with respect to strain, $\sigma_{ij} = \partial \mathcal{U}_E / \partial \varepsilon_{ij}$, such that the effective stress in the hydrogel material is

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2G \left(\varepsilon_{ij} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} \varepsilon_{kk} \delta_{ij} \right) - \alpha p \delta_{ij}, \quad (10)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. $p = -K_f \zeta$ is the pressure (a negative stress) in the fluid and α is a dimensionless geometry coefficient characterizing volume change of the fluid relative to the volume change of the material element. Mechanical equilibrium is given by setting the summed partial derivatives of the effective stress to zero, $\partial \sigma_{ij,i} = 0$, to give

$$2G \left(\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{kk}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{kk}}{\partial x_i} \right) - \alpha \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} = 0. \quad (11)$$

Rearranging, and assuming that the dilatational strain is homogeneous within a hydrogel material element, $\varepsilon_{kk} = \zeta$, gives

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} = \frac{2G(1-\nu)}{\alpha(1-2\nu)} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x_i} \quad (12)$$

This equation connects pressure and relative volume change gradients in the interstitial fluid in the constraining presence of the solid skeleton.

Extension of the above analysis to non equilibrium time dependent poroelastic deformation requires two additional constraints on fluid motion. The first constraint is the conservation of fluid, requiring the time rate of change of fluid volume within a material element to equal the sum of the spatial gradients of flux out of the element,

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial J_i}{\partial x_i}, \quad (13)$$

where J_i is a fluid flux (rate of fluid volume passing through an area). The second constraint is a relationship between flux and pressure gradient, here given by empirical Darcy's law

$$J_i = - \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i}, \quad (14)$$

where k is the permeability of the hydrogel to fluid flow and μ is the viscosity of the fluid. Combining Eqs. (12)–(14) gives

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = c \nabla^2 p, \quad (15)$$

where the consolidation coefficient c is given by

$$c = \frac{2(1-\nu)}{(1-2\nu)} \frac{Gk}{\alpha\mu}. \quad (16)$$

Equation (15) has the familiar form of a diffusive transport equation and the consolidation coefficient c of Eq. (16) plays the role of a diffusivity. The interpretation of these equations is that a perturbation in the local pressure p is “diffused” away by transport of the fluid through the deforming and permeable solid, or that deformation of the solid creating such perturbations is accommodated by fluid flow. Stiff, permeable solids and small viscosity fluids speed this transport and accommodation. The dimensions of c are those of all diffusivity terms, $[c] = \text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, and it is noted that c involves both equilibrium and transport parameters (for homogeneous fluids c can be interpreted as a self diffusion coefficient). As with mass and thermal transport phenomena described by diffusion equations similar to Eq. (15) (Carslaw and Jaeger 1946; Shewmon 1989), variation in a characteristic length scale L for fluid transport in time t in a poroelastic system is $L \sim (ct)^{1/2}$.

The partial differential equation of Eq. (15) and definition of Eq. (16) were originally derived by Biot (1941a) using equations similar to Eqs. (9)–(14) (with some changes in notation). A major motivation for the work of Biot was the creep, or consolidation or settlement, of water saturated soils in loaded structural foundations. Biot thus applied Eq. (15) to descriptions of soil consolidation in step loaded confined compression and plane strain compression geometries (Biot 1941ab; Biot and Clingan 1941). Subsequent studies that focused on indentation-like geometries in soil consolidation included spherical step loading (Agbezuge and Deresiewicz 1974) and circular flat punch step loading (Selvadurai and Yue 1993 and following). In these later works, Eqs. (10)–(14) and (16) or similar are given as starting equations and Eq. (15) is implied. In all cases (Biot 1941ab; Biot and Clingan 1941; Agbezuge and Deresiewicz 1974; Selvadurai and Yue 1993), extensive mathematical sophistication and complexity is required to solve the partial differential Eq. (15) and match the appropriate poroelastic boundary conditions (and more detailed analysis adds more terms, Detournay and Cheng 1993). Nevertheless, three simple relations were made clear in these analyses, particularly in that of Agbezuge and Deresiewicz. First, the dimensionless group $\gamma = (ct)^{1/2}/a$ enables time and indentation length scale effects to be expressed simultaneously by a single parameter γ . Second, the initial and final variables in a poroelastic experiment are related by a simple function of the Poisson’s ratio ν of the drained solid. For example, for indentation creep experiments at fixed load this function is $h(\infty) = [2(1 - 2\nu)]^{2/3}h(0)$. Third, the “reduced” variable in a poroelastic experiment is a universal function of the dimensionless parameter γ . For indentation creep experiments this variable is $[h(t) - h(0)]/[h(\infty) - h(0)] = g(\gamma)$, where the function $g(\gamma)$ is independent of indenter radius and contact load. An aid to using these relations is to approximate $g(\gamma)$ by a simple function that can be fit to experimental data. Such a fit was developed and used by Oyen (2008) to describe indentation creep.

The analogous simple relations applicable to poroelastic indentation relaxation are slightly different from those above. First, as contact radius is fixed in relaxation experiments a dimensionless group linear in time is more intuitive,

$$\tau = ct/a^2. \quad (17)$$

Second, the initial and final variables of interest in an indentation relaxation experiment at fixed displacement are the initial and final loads, which are related through poroelastic effects by

$$P_0 = 2(1 - \nu)P_\infty. \quad (18)$$

Third, the reduced variable in relaxation experiments involves indentation loads and is a universal function of the new dimensionless parameter and given by

$$\frac{P(t) - P_\infty}{P_0 - P_\infty} = g(\tau), \quad (19)$$

where $g(\tau)$ is independent of indenter radius and contact displacement. As in descriptions of creep, an aid to using these relations in descriptions of indentation relaxation is to approximate $g(\tau)$ by a simple function that can be fit to experimental data. A group of such functions was developed by [Hu et al. \(2010\)](#) through empirical fitting to the results of finite element analyses of indentation relaxation. The functions are of the form

$$g(\tau) = \alpha_p \exp(-\beta_1 \tau) + (1 - \alpha_p) \exp(-\beta_2 \tau^{1/2}), \quad (20)$$

where the dimensionless α and β numerical terms depend on the shape of the indenter (spherical, circular flat punch, conical, plane strain flat punch) and are of order unity. Over the domain of τ , $(0, \infty)$, the range of $g(\tau)$ is $(1, 0)$. Equations (17)–(20) were used by Hu and colleagues to describe spherical ([Hu et al. 2010, 2011a](#)) and conical ([Hu et al. 2011b, 2012](#)) indentation relaxation in a series of chemically cross linked fluid filled gel systems and by Islam and colleagues to describe spherical indentation relaxation in a series of chemically and physically cross linked gels and hydrogels in water ([Islam et al. 2021ab](#); includes a typographical error in $g(\tau)$). Physical insight is gained by recognizing that the expression for P_0 , the indentation load on initial contact, given by [Agbezugbe and Deresiewicz \(1974\)](#) is

$$P_0 = \frac{16Ga^3}{3R}, \quad (21)$$

and that the expression for P_∞ , the indentation load at final relaxation, given by Eq. (4) is

$$P_\infty = \frac{8Ga^3}{3(1 - \nu)R}. \quad (22)$$

Combining Eqs. (21) and (22) leads to Eq. (18) and Eq. (21) can be gained by setting $\nu = 0.5$ in Eq. (22). An interpretation is that on initial contact a fluid filled gel behaves as an incompressible material with indentation modulus proportional to G . On final relaxation the drained gel behaves as a compressible elastic material with indentation modulus proportional to $G/[2(1 - \nu)]$. Eq. (20) provides the kinetic linkage between these two equilibrium states.

2.4 Poroviscoelastic Deformation

If the time dependent deformation kinetics of a hydrogel are determined by the simultaneous effects of poroelastic deformation of the hydrogel fluid + solid phases and viscoelastic deformation of the solid polymer skeleton, the deformation can be described as *poroviscoelastic*. Such deformation can be described by finite element analyses (Galli et al. 2011; Strange et al. 2013) and analytically (Strange et al. 2013). The simplest analytical description assumes the poroelastic and viscoelastic effects are separable and this approach is now considered.

Analysis begins by combining Eqs. (18) and (19) to eliminate P_0 in favor of ν to rewrite the poroelastic response as

$$P(t) = P_\infty [(1 - 2\nu)g(\tau) + 1]. \quad (23)$$

Similarly, the viscoelastic response of Eq. (8) is rewritten as

$$P_V(t) = P_\infty [f(\tau) + 1], \quad (24)$$

where

$$f(\tau) = \alpha_V \exp(-\beta_V \tau), \quad (25)$$

and α_V and β_V are empirical dimensionless parameters of order unity. Over the domain of τ , $(0, \infty)$, the range of $f(\tau)$ is $(\alpha_V, 0)$. The separable poroviscoelastic response is obtained by replacing P_∞ in Eq. (24) with $P_V(t)$ of Eq. (25) to obtain

$$P(t) = P_\infty [f(\tau) + 1] [(1 - 2\nu)g(\tau) + 1]. \quad (26)$$

Over the domain of τ the range of $P(t)/P_\infty$ is $(2(1 + \alpha_V)(1 - \nu), 1)$. For spherical indentation relaxation experiments it is convenient to express the equilibrium indentation load in terms of indentation strain and indenter radius, Eq. (5), as

$$P_\infty = \frac{8G}{3(1 - \nu)} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{0.2} \right)^3 R^2 \quad (27)$$

and the dimensionless group including time, Eq. (17), similarly as

$$\tau = \frac{ct}{R^2} \left(\frac{0.2}{\varepsilon} \right)^2. \quad (28)$$

Equations (26)–(28) can be used in two methods to characterize time dependent spherical indentation relaxation. The first method has an empirical focus and recognizes that the experimental variables $P(t)/R^2$ and t/R^2 are related by a function of material parameters $G, \nu, \alpha_V, \beta_V$ and indentation strain ε that is independent of sphere radius R and the exact forms of $f(\tau)$ and $g(\tau)$. Hence a plot of $P(t)/R^2$ and t/R^2 should collapse all experimental relaxation data for a single material tested at fixed indentation strain onto a universal response. The second

method has an analytical focus and uses the given forms of $f(\tau)$ and $g(\tau)$, Eqs. (20) and (24), to fit $P(t)$ data using ε and R as inputs and $G, \nu, \alpha_V, \beta_V$ and c as fitting parameters.

3. Experiment

3.1 Base Material

Figure 1 shows a logarithmic plot of the spherical indentation load relaxation data of [Strange et al. \(2013\)](#) using the contact radius adjusted experimental coordinates of $P(t)/R^2$ and t/R^2 . The data were supplemented with additional raw data ([Oyen, M.L, private communication 2023](#)). All data describe the behavior of a single 3 % agar hydrogel material tested in water. The indentation radii were $R = 12.7$ mm, 7.9 mm, 4.8 mm, and 3.2 mm and the indentation strain in all cases was $\varepsilon = 0.05$. The contact displacements were thus in the range 0.8 mm–0.2 mm and the conjugate contact radii in the range 3.2 mm–0.8 mm. Symbols indicate the central response for each radius; relative dispersion of the four to five responses for each radius was approximately $\pm 10\%$, about twice the symbol size. In adjusted coordinates the load relaxation behaviors for the different radii indenters collapse onto a universal response. Relaxation over the periods of measurement was approximately a factor of three, indicated by the vertical arrow.

The poroelastic based scaling of Eq. (27) and (28) clearly connects the relaxation data obtained at different contact dimensions suggesting that poroelastic length scale effects are a significant factor in the deformation response. However, the data also suggest that a length scale invariant viscoelastic factor is also significant. The solid line in Figure 1 shows the predicted behavior if poroelastic effects alone determine relaxation. The response was determined from Eq. (26) setting $\alpha_V = f(\tau) = 0$, $\alpha_P = 0.491$, $\beta_1 = 0.908$, and $\beta_2 = 1.679$ in Eq. (20) ([Hu et al. 2010](#)), and $\nu = 0.32$ typical of hydrogels ([Strange et al. 2013](#)). The line has been shifted such that the median response is aligned with that of the experimental data. Although the time scale over which the predicted relaxation takes place is consistent with the experimental observations the magnitude is significantly less, about 1.3, Eq. (18), than that observed, about 3.0. Clearly, viscoelastic effects are contributing simultaneously to the relaxation. (It is possible to describe the data using poroelastic effects alone using unphysical Poisson's ratios of $\nu \approx -0.7$; [Strange et al. 2013](#); [Islam et al 2021ab](#).)

Figure 1. Logarithmic plot of spherical indentation load relaxation of agar hydrogels deformed to 0.05 indentation strain. Four different indenter radii were used, indicated by the different symbols. The use of adjusted coordinates collapses all data to a universal response.

Figure 2 shows a logarithmic plot of the spherical indentation load relaxation data of Figure 1 using the experimental coordinates of $P(t)$ and t . The individual indenter radii are indicated; the symbols are as in Figure 1. The vertical arrow indicates a factor of three. The solid lines in Figure 2 represent a visual best fit to the data using a single set of poroviscoelastic material parameters and Eq. (26)–(28). The α_p , β_1 , β_2 , and ν values are as above with the addition of $\alpha_v = 1.2$, $\beta_v = 0.5$, $G = 51.5$ kPa, and $c = 4 \times 10^{-2}$ mm² s⁻¹. Although there are some deviations, the fits well describe the data for all four radii, including the shift to shorter times for relaxation at smaller indenters.

Figure 2. Logarithmic plot of spherical indentation load relaxation of agar hydrogels deformed to 0.05 indentation strain using indenter radii indicated. Solid lines are poroviscoelastic fits to the data using a single set of material parameters.

3.2 Chemically Altered Materials

Chemically altered hydrogels were fabricated by adding 50 % or 75% glycerol (by mass) to the agar-water mixture prior to gelation. The goal was to add hydrophilic side groups to the agar chains forming the polymeric hydrogel skeleton and thereby impede the migration of water through the hydrogel. Figure 3 shows a logarithmic plot of the spherical indentation load relaxation data of the altered materials using the experimental coordinates of $P(t)$ and t . The individual indenter radii are indicated; the open and filled symbols indicate the responses of the 50% and 75 % materials, respectively. The dashed lines indicate the responses of the base material over the domain of measurements. The solid lines represent a visual best fit to the 75% altered material data using a single set of poroviscoelastic material parameters and Eq. (26)–(28). The α_p , β_1 , β_2 , α_v , and β_v values are as above. The elastic properties are altered in a minor way to $G = 53$ kPa and $\nu = 0.3$. The consolidation coefficient is decreased significantly to $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Although there are some deviations, the fits well describe the data for both radii.

Figure 3. Logarithmic plot of spherical indentation load relaxation of agar-glycerol hydrogels deformed to 0.05 indentation strain using indenter radii indicated. Solid lines are poroviscoelastic fits to the data using a single set of material parameters. Dashed lines indicate responses of base material.

The major point to be observed in Figure 3 is that the chemical alteration of the base agar hydrogel had the intended effect of impeding the migration of water without altering the elastic properties of the gel. There was little difference in the responses of the 50% and 75% materials, but both were clearly much retarded in relaxation relative to the base material.

4. Summary

This report strengthens the conclusions of [Strange et al. \(2013\)](#) that the deformation properties of physically cross linked hydrogels are described by the simultaneous actions of viscoelastic and poroelastic effects. These combined actions lead to much greater indentation relaxation than that observed in chemically cross linked gels, which are restricted to poroelastic deformation ([Hu et al. 2010, 2011ab, 2012](#); [Islam et al. 2021b](#)). The report also strengthens the contention of [Galli et al.](#) and [Strange et al.](#) that the poroelastic and viscoelastic responses are separable in these materials. The separability was demonstrated here on a base agar hydrogel and in chemically altered materials in which the poroelastic response was “tuned” independently of the viscoelastic response. Improvements to the analyses could include addition of ramp correction factors to better describe short time relaxation behavior and addition of multiple viscoelastic time constants to better describe long time relaxation behavior; such deviations from the analyses are visible here in Figure 1.

Acknowledgements

M.L. Oyen is thanked for provision of the M. Eng. thesis of H. Brawn.

References

- Agbezuge, L.K. and Deresiewicz, H. (1974). On the indentation of a consolidating half-space. *Israel Journal of Technology* 12: 322–338.
- Biot, M.A. (1941a). General theory of three-dimensional consolidation. *Journal of Applied Physics* 12: 155–164.
- Biot, M.A. (1941b). Consolidation settlement under a rectangular load distribution. *Journal of Applied Physics* 12: 426–430.
- Biot, M.A. and Clingan, F.M. (1941). Consolidation settlement of a soil with an impervious top surface. *Journal of Applied Physics* 12: 578–581.
- Carslaw, H.S. and Jaeger, J.C. (1946). *Conduction of Heat in Solids*. Oxford.
- Detournay, E. and Cheng, A.H.-D. (1993). Fundamentals of poroelasticity. In *Comprehensive Rock Engineering: Principles, Practice and Projects, Vol. II, Analysis and Design Method*. Ed Fairhurst, C. Pergamon.
- Galli, M., Fornasiere, E., Cugnoni, J., and Oyen, M.L. (2011). Poroviscoelastic characterization of particle-reinforced gelatin gels using indentation and homogenization. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials* 4: 610–617.
- Howell, P., Kozyreff, G., and Ockendon, J. (2009). *Applied Solid Mechanics*. Cambridge.
- Hu, Y., Zhao, X., Vlassak, J.J., and Suo, Z. (2010). Using indentation to characterize the poroelasticity of gels. *Applied Physics Letters* 96: 121904.
- Hu, Y., Chan, E.P., Vlassak, J.J. and Suo, Z. (2011a). Poroelastic relaxation indentation of thin layers of gels. *Journal of Applied Physics* 110: 086103.
- Hu, Y., Chen, X., Whitesides, G.M., Vlassak, J.J., and Suo, Z. (2011b). Indentation of polydimethylsiloxane submerged in organic solvents. *Journal of Materials Research* 26: 785–795.

- Hu, Y., You, J.O., Auguste, D.T., Suo, Z., and Vlassak, J.J. (2012). Indentation: A simple, nondestructive method for characterizing the mechanical and transport properties of pH-sensitive hydrogels. *Journal of Materials Research* 27: 152–160.
- Islam, M.R. and Oyen, M.L. (2021a). A poroelastic master curve for time-dependent and multiscale mechanics of hydrogels. *Journal of Materials Research* 36: 2582–2590.
- Islam, M.R. and Oyen, M.L. (2021b). Load-relaxation characteristics of chemical and physical hydrogels as soft tissue mimics. *Experimental Mechanics* 61: 939–949.
- Johnson, K.L. (1985). *Contact Mechanics*. Cambridge.
- Selvadurai, A.P.S. and Yue, Z.Q. (1993). A contact problem in poroelasticity. *WIT Transactions on Engineering Sciences* 1: 285–296.
- Shewmon, P. (1989). *Diffusion in Solids*. The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society.
- Strange, D.G., Fletcher, T.L., Tonsomboon, K., Brawn, H., Zhao, X., and Oyen, M.L. (2013). Separating poroviscoelastic deformation mechanisms in hydrogels. *Applied Physics Letters* 102: 031913.
- Wang, H.F. (2000). *Theory of Linear Poroelasticity*. Princeton.